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Research Article

Development and Validation of a Stability-Indicating RP-HPLC Method for the Quantification of Sitagliptin and Dapagliflozin in Bulk Drug and Commercial Formulation

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ABSTRACT

Anti-diabetic medications dapagliflozin and sitagliptin phosphate are used to treat Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) by reconsumption of glucose in the kidney (SGLT-2 inhibitor) and prohibiting the activity of dipeptidyl peptidase-4 (DPP-4), respectively. The linearity, accuracy, and precision criteria were developed and validated using the liquid spectrophotometric (HPLC) technique. To provide a straightforward, precise, correct (accurate) and specific High Performance Liquid Chromatographic approach for the Estimation of dapagliflozin and sitagliptin phosphate. Methanol and water (50:50) were used as a diluent in the development of the HPLC technique, which had wavelengths of 224 nm for dapagliflozin and 265 nm for sitagliptin phosphate. For both drugs, the linearity range was found to be between 0 and 25 ug/ml and between 0 and 125 ug/ml, with correlation coefficients of 0.9998 and 0.9997, respectively. For both drugs, the developed method's %RSD value was less than 2, indicating its precision. In accordance with the ICH Q2 (R1) recommendations, precision and results were statistically examined intra-day (0.40%) (1.87%) and inter-day (1.35%) (1.44%). According to the results in this paper, a straightforward, quick, and economically feasible spectroscopic approach for estimating dapagliflozin and sitagliptin phosphate has been developed and validated. The Developed technique may be used for routine analysis and quality control of the listed medications, either alone or in combination for Both Drugs.

INTRODUCTION

Dapagliflozin

Dapagliflozin, a drug in the gliflozin family, is used for the treatment of type 2 diabetes [1]. Dapagliflozin restricts the sodium-glucose

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transport proteins (SGLT2) class 2, which are responsible for around 90% of the kidney's glucose reconsumption [2]. In the renal proximal tubule, sodium-glucose co-transporter 2 (SGLT2) reabsorbs both glucose and sodium chloride. Dapagliflozin is an SGLT2 restrictor that increases renal glucose elimination in order to treat hyperglycemia in type 2 diabetes. When this transporter activity is blocked, blood glucose is eliminated through urine [3]. The Molecular formula of dapagliflozin is $C_{21}H_{25}ClO_6$. A white to off-white crystalline powder, dapagliflozin dissolves in Methanol, Acetonitrile (ACN), ethanol and other organic solvents [4,5].

Dapagliflozin chemical Name: (2S,3R,4R,5S,6R)-2-{4-chloro-3-[(4-ethoxy phenyl) methyl] phenyl}-6-(hydroxymethyl) oxane-3,4,5-triol. [6]

Figure.1: Structure of Dapagliflozin

1. Sitagliptin Phosphate

Sitagliptin phosphate is an oral blocker of dipeptidyl peptidase-4 (DPP-4). This enzyme-inhibiting drug is used individually or in combination with other oral antihyperglycemic drugs to treat type 2 diabetes. Sitagliptin restricts the DPP-4 by a competitive mechanism. This enzyme breaks down incretins, which are digestive hormones released after a meal and are also known as GLP-1 and GIP [7]. The pancreas is able to limit the release of glucagon and boost the production of insulin by blocking Gastric Inhibitory Polypeptide (GIP) and Glucagon-like Peptide-1

(GLP-1) inactivation [8]. Blood glucose levels proceed near to normal as a result. The Molecular formula of Sitagliptin Phosphate is Molecular $C_{16}H_{15}F_6N_5O$. It is slightly soluble in acetone and soluble in water, methanol, ethanol, and other solvents. [9,10]

Sitagliptin chemical Name: 7 - [(3R) - 3 - amino - 1 - oxo - 4 - (2, 4, 5-trifluorophenyl) butyl] - 5, 6, 7, 8 tetrahydro - 3 (trifluoromethyl)-1, 2, 4 - triazolo [4, 3-a] pyrazine phosphate [11]

Figure.2: Structure of Sitagliptin

The review of the literature demonstrated that UV spectroscopy and RP-HPLC were used to quantify the drug from bulk [12]. The recommended study demonstrates a simple to operate, quick, and affordable RP-HPLC technique for Quantify Dapagliflozin and Sitagliptin in Formulation and API [13,14,15]. In accordance with ICH Standards, the Established technique was verified for Linearity, Accuracy, Precision, Limit of Detection (LOD), Limit of Quantification (LOQ), Robustness, Ruggedness, and sensitivity. Additionally, stress testing was done in a variety of Environments, including temperature, light, oxidation, humidity, and pH (acid/base). [16]

MATERIAL AND METHOD:

Chemical and Reagents:

Table.1: Chemical and Reagents

SR. No	Chemicals and Drug	Grade	Manufacturer
1.	Methanol	HPLC Grade	Actylis Chemicals
2.	Acetonitrile (ACN)	HPLC Grade	Actylis Chemicals
3.	Dapagliflozin	Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient (API)	Micro Lab. India
4.	Sitagliptin	Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient (API)	Micro Lab. India

Instruments:**Table.2: Instruments used for Experiment**

SR. No	Instrument Name	Model Name
1.	UV Spectrophotometer	Shimadzu UV 1800
2.	UV Software	UV Probe
3.	HPLC	JASCO Extrema LC- 4000
4.	HPLC Software	ChromNAV
5.	Ultra Sonicator	Life care Equipment
6	Electronic Weighing Balance	Shimadzu (sensitivity 0.001gm)

ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT BY HPLC METHOD**1. Dapagliflozin:****Determination of solubility for HPLC analysis**

A specific quantity of the standard medication was dissolved in a variety of solvents, including acetonitrile, methanol, and water. The UV technique was used to estimate solubility quantitatively.

Selecting an appropriate solvent: A 50:50 v/v composition of water to methanol was used as the solvent. Based on studies on solubility choice solvents and solubility experiments conducted on a number of solvents, the solvent was chosen.

Formation of stock solution for standard

10 mg of dapagliflozin were carefully measured and pour into a 10-milliliter volumetric flask, diluted with 50:50 water and methanol, and then sonicated to the appropriate concentration of 1000 µg/mL to create the standard stock solution. A 1 mL aliquot of the previously mentioned standard stock solution was put into a 10 mL volumetric flask. It was then diluted with 50:50 water and methanol to achieve the required concentration, which resulted in a sub-stock solution of 100 µg/mL.

Formation of stock solution for sample

To make the sample stock solution, five pills were accurately weighed and crushed into powder. A volume equal to 10 mg were weighted and pour into a 10-milliliter volumetric flask, diluted with 50:50 water and methanol, and sonicated for 15 minutes. 1 mL of the previously stated sample stock solution, diluted with water: methanol (50:50), was added to a 10-milliliter volumetric flask to create the solution with a concentration of 100 µg/mL.

Detection of Wavelength for Dapagliflozin

The standard solution of 10 µg/mL of Dapagliflozin was prepared and scanned over the 400-200nm range. After the scan was completed, it showed maximum absorbance at 224 nm, so the detection wavelength was selected as 224 nm.

Figure.3: Spectrum of Dapagliflozin.**2. Sitagliptin phosphate****Determination of solubility for HPLC analysis**

A specific quantity of the standard medication was dissolved in a variety of solvents, including acetonitrile, methanol, and water. The UV

technique was used to estimate solubility quantitatively.

Selecting an appropriate solvent: A 50:50 v/v composition of water to methanol was used as the solvent. Based on studies on solubility choice solvents and solubility experiments conducted on a number of solvents, the solvent was chosen.

Formation of stock solution for standard

10 mg of Sitagliptin Phosphate were carefully measured and pour into a 10-milliliter volumetric flask, diluted with 50:50 water and methanol, and then sonicated to the appropriate concentration of 1000 µg/mL to create the standard stock solution.

Formation of stock solution for sample

To make the sample stock solution, five pills were accurately weighed and crushed into powder. A volume equal to 100 mg were weighted and pour into a 100-milliliter volumetric flask, diluted with 50:50 water and methanol, and sonicated for 15 minutes.

Detection of wavelength for Sitagliptin Phosphate

The standard solution of 100 µg/mL of Sitagliptin Phosphate was prepared and scanned over the 400-200nm range. After the scan was completed, it showed maximum absorbance at 265 nm, so the detection wavelength was selected as 265 nm.

Figure.4: Spectrum of Sitagliptin Phosphate

Chromatographic Conditions

Table.3: Chromatographic Conditions

Sr no.	Specification	Description
1	Equipment	JASCO Extrema LC- 4000
2	Software	ChromNAV
3	Column	BDS Hypersil C ₁₈ (250 x 4.6 mm, 5µm)
4	Wavelength	i. Dapagliflozin: 224 nm ii. Sitagliptin Phosphate: 265 nm
5	Column temperature	25°C
6	Flowrate	0.8 mL/min
7	Injection volume	10 µL
8	Run time	10 min
9	Mobile phase	Water: Acetonitrile (60:40)
10	Diluent	Water: Methanol (50:50)

ANALYTICAL METHOD VALIDATION BY HPLC METHOD

1. Specificity study

To illustrate the specificity of the described approach, the following solutions were prepared and injected.

Diluent is used as a blank solution. (Methanol: Water 50:50)

Standard solution: Standard solution was produced, in accord with the ICH Guidelines.

Sample solution: Sample solution was produced, in accord with the ICH Guidelines.

Verify the drug's peak and interference study identification.

2. Linearity

10 ml volumetric flask was filled with 10 mg of the drug, which had been carefully weighed. The solvent was then added to dilute the drug to the required concentration of 1000 µg/mL. Using the previously described solution, the drug's linear response was determined for Dapagliflozin (0–25 µg/mL) and Sitagliptin Phosphate (0–125 µg/mL), respectively. The calibration curve indicated peak area as a function of concentration. We calculated the correlation coefficient and Y-intercept of the linearity curve.

3. Accuracy

According to the analytical method, a known quantity of drug X was spiked into sample solutions in triplicate to produce drug concentrations that were proportional to the working concentration, 80%, 100%, and 120%. This data was then used to evaluate the procedure's accuracy. One estimated the percentage of recovery.

4. Precision

Figure.5: Standard Peak of Dapagliflozin

Linearity for Dapagliflozin

A standard solution comprising 125 µg/mL of sitagliptin phosphate and 25 µg/mL of dapagliflozin was used for six injections into the system. The chromatogram was recorded, and the % RSD of the Peak Area was then calculated.

I. Intraday precision:

A standard peak's responses were measured on the same day with the same concentration solution in order to determine the Intraday precision.

II. Interday Precision:

A standard peak's responses were measured on a different day with the same concentration solution in order to determine the Interday precision.

5. Limit of Detection (LOD) & Limit of Quantification (LOQ)

Six sets of linearity concentrations were assessed based on the response and slope of a regression equation, and LOD and LOQ were calculated using the following calculations in accordance with ICH guidelines.

6. Robustness

The following parameters and their effect on the system suitability test have been changed one by one. In accordance with ICH Guidelines, change in flowrate (± 0.2 ml/min); Change in temperature ($\pm 5^\circ\text{C}$); Change in wavelength (± 2 nm).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Specificity

Standard Peaks of Dapagliflozin and Sitagliptin Phosphate

Figure.6: Standard Peak of Sitagliptin Phosphate

The linearity of the drug Dapagliflozin was assessed by dilutions produced using the standard

stock solution. The concentration range spanned by the dilutions was 0–25 µg/mL.

Table.4: Linearity for Dapagliflozin

Concentration (ug/mL)	Area
0	0
5	150701
10	313798
15	471066
20	620803
25	771181

Linearity for Sitagliptin Phosphate

The linearity of the drug Sitagliptin Phosphate was assessed by dilutions produced using the standard

Table.5: Linearity for Sitagliptin Phosphate

Concentration (ug/mL)	Area
0	0
25	122992
50	251855
75	366288
100	495142
125	626220

Accuracy for Dapagliflozin

80%, 100%, and 120% of three distinct concentrations' percentage drug accuracy. Using

Table.6: Accuracy for Dapagliflozin

Level	Peak area	Actual Concentration	Calculated Concentration	Mean Concentration	% recovery	Standard deviation	%RSD
80%	553612	18	17.8809	17.9953	99.97%	0.10504	0.58373
	560011		18.0873				
	557852		18.0177				
100%	620778	20	20.0481	20.1504	100.75%	0.23133	1.14803
	632155		20.4152				
	618909		19.9878				
120%	680022	22	21.9598	22.0794	100.36%	0.08731	0.39543
	679651		21.9478				
	684512		22.1047				

Figure.7: Calibration curve of Dapagliflozin by HPLC

stock solution. The concentration range spanned by the dilutions was 0–125 µg/mL.

Figure.8: Calibration curve of Sitagliptin Phosphate by HPLC

the information gathered from the recovery experiments, the mean recovery % was then computed.

Figure.9: 80% Chromatogram

Figure.10: 100% Chromatogram

Figure.11: 120 % Chromatogram

Accuracy for Sitagliptin Phosphate

80%, 100%, and 120% of three distinct concentrations' percentage drug accuracy. Using

the information gathered from the recovery experiments, the mean recovery % was then computed.

Table.7: Accuracy for Sitagliptin Phosphate

Level	Peak area	Actual Concentration (ug/mL)	Calculated Concentration (ug/mL)	Mean Concentration (ug/mL)	% recovery	Standard Deviation	%RSD
80%	458782	90	91.80	90.88	100.98%	0.90396	0.99464
	449772		89.99				
	454087		90.86				
100%	492633	100	98.59	98.37	98.37%	0.75599	0.76855
	487321		97.52				
	494608		98.99				
120%	551455	110	110.39	109.26	99.33%	1.01089	0.92523
	541744		108.44				
	544263		108.95				

Figure.12: 80% Chromatogram

Figure.13: 100% Chromatogram

Figure.14: 120% Chromatogram

Precision for Dapagliflozin:

Both intraday (repeatability assessed by analysing the standard solution on the same day) and interday methods (repeatability conducted by analysing the standard solution on different day)

were used to analyse precision. Injecting the standard solution six times was the method used for this precision investigation. The slope is used to express the results.

Intraday Precision

Table.8: Intraday Precision for Dapagliflozin

Sample Name	Test 1	Test 2	Test 3	Test 4	Test 5	Test 6	Mean	SD	% RSD
Area	771097	773627	774876	774491	775453	767379	772820.5	3071.69	0.40
Theoretical Plate	10979	10935	10858	10844	10834	10963	10902.17	64.29	0.59
Tailing Factor	1.199	1.203	1.204	1.196	1.198	1.187	1.20	0.01	0.51
Retention Time	4.18	4.17	4.17	4.16	4.16	4.17	4.17	0.01	0.21

Figure.15: Chromatogram of Intraday Precision for Dapagliflozin

Interday Precision

Table.9: Interday Precision for Dapagliflozin

Sample Name	Test 1	Test 2	Test 3	Test 4	Test 5	Test 6	Mean	SD	% RSD
Area	766751	781503	776824	762451	764087	788194	773302	10459.53	1.35
Theoretical Plate	11100	11072	10699	11098	10806	10922	10949.5	169.59	1.55
Tailing Factor	1.183	1.179	1.187	1.144	1.16	1.173	1.2	0.02	1.39
Retention Time	4.17	4.16	4.13	4.13	4.13	4.14	4.14	0.02	0.43

Figure.16: Chromatogram of Interday Precision for Dapagliflozin

Precision for Sitagliptin Phosphate

In this level of accuracy investigation, the standard solution was injected six times; the results were expressed using the slope. Both intraday (repeatability evaluated by analyzing the standard

solution on the same day) and interday methods (repeatability carried out by analyzing the standard solution on Different day) were employed to analyze precision.

Intraday Precision

Table 10 Intraday Precision for Sitagliptin Phosphate

Sample Name	Test 1	Test 2	Test 3	Test 4	Test 5	Test 6	Mean	SD	% RSD
Area	636637	636692	623069	610097	638115	618221	627138.5	11734.31	1.87
Theoretical Plate	5425	5423	5496	5521	5463	5484	5468.67	39.36	0.72
Tailing Factor	1.433	1.445	1.384	1.415	1.448	1.404	1.42	0.03	1.76
Retention Time	4.96	4.97	4.98	5	5.04	5.01	4.99	0.03	0.6

Figure.17: Chromatogram of Intraday Precision for Sitagliptin Phosphate

Table.11: Interday Precision for Sitagliptin Phosphate

Sample Name	Test 1	Test 2	Test 3	Test 4	Test 5	Test 6	Mean	SD	% RSD
Area	622046	615982	608947	603070	604414	623561	613003	8843.17	1.44
Theoretical Plate	5672	5800	5867	5800	5801	5653	5765.5	84.07	1.46
Tailing Factor	1.417	1.481	1.484	1.44	1.454	1.472	1.5	0.02	1.15
Retention Time	4.82	4.83	4.84	4.84	4.87	4.85	4.8	0.02	0.38

Figure.18: Chromatogram of Interday Precision for Sitagliptin Phosphate

Robustness

The system suitability test has been affected by the gradual changes made to the following parameters.

- I. Change in flowrate ± 0.2 ml/min (0.6mL and 1mL)
- II. Change in temperature $\pm 5^\circ\text{C}$ (20°C and 30°C)

- III. Change in wavelength ± 2 nm [Dapagliflozin (222nm and 226nm)]
[Sitagliptin Phosphate (263nm and 267nm)]

1. Dapagliflozin

Table.12: Robustness Data of Dapagliflozin

SR NO.		1	2	3	MEAN	SD	%RSD
0.6 ml/min	AREA	418254	411648	424602	418168	6477.43	1.55
	RT	5.437	5.543	5.533	6	0.06	1.06

FLOW RATE	1 ml/min	NTP	10713	10828	10812	10784	62.29	0.58
		AREA	251209	247123	251423	249918	2423.19	0.97
		RT	3.327	3.333	3.337	3	0.01	0.15
		NTP	9273	9271	9253	9266	11.02	0.12
TEMP	20°C	AREA	331684	323588	323312	326195	4755.9	1.46
		RT	4.183	4.183	4.163	4	0.01	0.28
		NTP	10701	10561	10600	10621	72.25	0.68
	30°C	AREA	315056	310931	315129	313705	2402.92	0.77
		RT	4.16	4.167	4.16	4	0.00	0.10
		NTP	10970	11115	11070	11052	74.22	0.67
WAVE LENGTH	222nm	AREA	313612	310612	309309	311178	2206.57	0.71
		RT	4.167	4.11	4.173	4	0.03	0.84
		NTP	10933	10938	11146	11006	121.56	1.10
	226nm	AREA	302471	297118	292973	297521	4761.79	1.60
		RT	4.177	4.167	4.107	4	0.04	0.91
		NTP	10871	11038	10831	10913	109.8	1.01

Figure.19: 0.6 mL Flow Rate

Figure.22: Temp. 30°C

Figure.20: 1mL Flow Rate

Figure.23: Wavelength 222

Figure.21: Temp. 20°C

Figure.24: Wavelength 226

2. Sitagliptin Phosphate

Table.13: Robustness Data of Sitagliptin Phosphate

SR NO.			1	2	3	MEAN	SD	%RSD
FLOW RATE	0.6ml/min	AREA	664637	683319	662454	670137	11468.3	1.71
		RT	6.87	6.763	6.77	7	0.06	0.88
		NTP	5875	5715	5883	5824	94.77	1.63
	1 ml/min	AREA	395616	385005	390815	391479	6829.73	1.74
		RT	4	4.07	4.023	4	0.04	0.89
		NTP	5728	5720	5810	5753	49.81	0.87
TEMP	20°C	AREA	479853	490162	479140	483052	6168.04	1.28
		RT	5.087	5.053	5.073	5	0.02	0.34
		NTP	6243	6178	6060	6160	92.77	1.51
	30°C	AREA	483654	481269	488993	484639	3955.02	0.82
		RT	5	4.923	4.913	5	0.05	0.96
		NTP	6044	6158	6124	6109	58.53	0.96
WAVE LENGTH	263 nm	AREA	473349	481451	471642	475481	5240.43	1.10
		RT	4.993	4.947	5.033	5	0.04	0.86
		NTP	6027	5987	5932	5981	47.57	0.8
	267 nm	AREA	489076	484329	496031	49812	5885.62	1.2
		RT	5.07	5.043	5.103	5	0.03	0.59
		NTP	5996	5847	5894	5912	76.17	1.29

Figure.25: 0.6 mL Flow Rate

Figure.26: 1 mL Flow Rate

Figure.27: Temp. 20°C

Figure.28: Temp. 30°C

Figure.29: Wavelength 263 nm

Figure.30: Wavelength 267 nm

Forced Degradation

Research on forced degradation can be used to investigate the quality of drug substance and drug product changes over time and in response to various climatic variables. They may be helpful in identifying the drug molecule's inherent stability,

the degradation route, the degradants, and proven stability-indicating analytical procedures. In accordance with ICH Guidelines, which are ICH Q1A, Q1B, and Q2B represent forced degradation. [17,18]

Dapagliflozin

Table.14: Degradation Data of Dapagliflozin

SR. No	Degradation	Procedure (10PPM)	% Degradation
1	Acid (1% HCL)	1mL Drug+ 1 mL HCL (for 24 hours)	5.34%
2	Base (1% NaOH)	1mL Drug+ 1 mL NaOH (for 24 hours)	9.09%
3	Oxidation (H ₂ O ₂)	1mL Drug+ 1 mL H ₂ O ₂ (for 24 hours)	13.1%
4	Photolytic	2 hours in UV Chamber	22.28%
5	Thermal	2 hours in Hot Air Oven (for 2 hours)	34.14%

Sitagliptin Phosphate

Table.15: Degradation Data of Sitagliptin Phosphate

SR. No	Degradation	Procedure (50PPM)	% Degradation
1	Acid (1% HCL)	1mL Drug+ 1 mL HCL (for 24 hours)	10.09%
2	Base (1% NaOH)	1mL Drug+ 1 mL NaOH (for 24 hours)	38.7 %
3	Oxidation (H ₂ O ₂)	1mL Drug+ 1 mL H ₂ O ₂ (for 24 hours)	3.37%
4	Photolytic	2 hours in UV Chamber	14.5%
5	Thermal	2 hours in Hot Air Oven (for 2 hours)	11.06%

CONCLUSION

The HPLC technique for measuring dapagliflozin and sitagliptin phosphate was properly designed and verified using a JASCO Extrema LC system-4000 HPLC model. The developed method for drug analysis is novel and makes use of a BDS Hypersil C18 (250 x 4.6 mm, ID 5µm) column and a specific wavelength of the respective drugs detected on a Shimadzu UV 1800 Spectrophotometer. There is a 10 µL injection volume. The ICH-compliant technique for

Dapagliflozin and Sitagliptin Phosphate was found to be simple, accurate, sensitive, fast, dependable, and reasonably priced. The analytical conditions were quickly established with a satisfactory resolution. It was found that the maximum percentage RSD for all parameters was less than 2%. The Developed technique is properly Estimated the Dapagliflozin and Sitagliptin Phosphate in labs and in industry for quality control purpose.

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